

Standard solutions of iron(III), bismuth(III) and thorium(IV) were prepared from ferric alum, bismuth nitrate and thorium nitrate respectively using AnalaR chemicals. The metal contents were determined by standard methods.

Standard EDTA solution was prepared from S. Merck's reagent grade Titriplex III. The solution was standardised against zinc solution using Erio T as indicator. This solution was diluted to obtain 0.01M solution of EDTA.

For the titration of iron(III) with EDTA, a 1% ethanolic solution of ASPHA was prepared. The iron-ASPHA complex (0.005M) was prepared by mixing 10 ml 0.05M ferric alum solution and 10 ml 0.01M ASPHA solution in ethanol, diluted to 100 ml with ethanol and used as indicator for the determination of bismuth and thorium.

Subtract the blank titre from the original titres. Typical results of titrations are given in Table 1.

Interferences :

The interferences of various ions are almost the same for Fe(III), Bi(III), and Th(IV) determinations since the titrations are performed in media of nearly the same pH range. Ions such as Ce(IV), Ti(IV), V(V), Nb(V) and Mo(VI) were eliminated prior to the titration by repeated extraction with a chloroform solution ($0.25\frac{W}{V}$) of ASPHA from 5M hydrochloric acid media. Alkaline earth metals and Al(III) were tolerated up to about 20-times excess, whereas Mg(II), Pb(II), Sb(III) and As(III) were tolerated only up to 10-times excess. Zn(II), Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) could be tolerated up to 5-times and Cu(II) interfered even in small amounts. Sn(II), Ta(V) and W(VI) interfered seriously.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON, BISMUTH and THORIUM

Iron taken (mg)	Iron found* (mg)	Standard Deviation	Bismuth taken (mg)	Bismuth found* (mg)	Standard Deviation	Thorium taken (mg)	Thorium found* (mg)	Standard Deviation
5.00	4.99	0.0014	5.43	5.43	0.0021	5.45	5.44	0.0012
10.00	10.02	0.0017	10.86	10.85	0.0018	10.91	10.90	0.0016
20.00	20.04	0.0016	21.73	21.77	0.0022	21.82	21.85	0.0018

* Average of six experiments

Procedure for Iron :

Take an aliquot of iron(III) solution containing about 10 mg of the metal and add enough 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution to give a faint turbidity. Add 12.5 ml of 0.2M potassium chloride and 5.1 ml of 0.2M hydrochloric acid. Dilute to 50 ml and adjust pH in the range 1.0-2.2 using hydrochloric acid or alkali. Add 1 ml of ASPHA solution and titrate against 0.01M EDTA. At the end point the colour of the solution changes from reddish violet to faint yellow.

Procedure for Bismuth or Thorium :

Measure out a suitable aliquot of bismuth or thorium solution and dilute the solution to 50 ml after adding 12.5 ml of 0.2M potassium chloride and 5.1 ml 0.2M hydrochloric acid. Adjust the pH in the range 0.7-2.3 for bismuth and 1.5-2.5 for thorium. Add 0.5 ml of iron-ASPHA complex and titrate slowly against EDTA. At the end point the reddish violet colour sharply changes to colourless.

In the titration of bismuth and thorium in which iron-ASPHA complex is the indicator, conduct a blank titration without the respective metal ions, keeping all the other components a constant.

Complexing anions like fluoride, oxalate, phosphate, and tartrate were tolerated only in small amounts.

References

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A Study of Interference of Cu(II) in Determination of Bismuth with Potassium Hexathiocyanato Chromate(III)*

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ROESLER¹ prepared $M_3Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot xH_2O$ from chrome alum and alkali thiocyanates. Dubskey and Wangenhofer² obtained $K_3Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ as

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